

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TOOLS USED IN INTERACTIVE LESSONS

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Abstract

The use of computer technologies as tools for learning, self-knowledge and reality. Consideration of the computer and other modern means of information technology as objects of study. Using new information technologies as a means of creative development of the student. The use of computer technology as a means of automating the processes of control, correction, testing and psychodiagnostics. Organization of communications based on the use of information technology tools for the purpose of transferring and acquiring pedagogical experience, methodological and educational literature.

Keywords: information, technology, equipment, interactive, board, education, presentation, demonstration, modeling

Using modern information technologies to organize intellectual leisure. Intensification and improvement of management of an educational institution and the educational process based on the use of a system of modern information technologies.

The capabilities of modern computer technology are largely adequate to the organizational, pedagogical and methodological needs of school education:

- computational - fast and accurate conversion of any type of information (numeric, text, graphic, sound, etc.);
- transducer - the ability of a computer to receive and output information in a wide variety of forms (if appropriate devices are available);
- combinatorial - the ability to remember, save, structure, sort large amounts of information, quickly find the necessary information;
- graphic - presentation of the results of your work in a clear visual form (text, audio, in the form of drawings, etc.);
- modeling - building information models (including dynamic ones) of real objects and phenomena.

Let's consider three key areas of application of interactive whiteboards in education:

- Presentations, demonstrations and simulations.
- How to use appropriate software and other resources in conjunction with the interactive whiteboard to improve understanding of lesson material.
- Increasing student activity in the lesson.
- How using an interactive whiteboard can increase student activity in the classroom.
- Increasing the pace of the lesson when using an interactive whiteboard.
- How using an interactive whiteboard can improve lesson planning and pace [1].

1. Presentations, demonstrations and simulations.

The interactive whiteboard is a valuable tool for whole-class learning. It is a visual resource that can help teachers make lessons lively and engaging for students. An interactive whiteboard allows you to present

information to students using a wide range of visualization tools (maps, tables, diagrams, diagrams, photographs, etc.).

Teachers can use interactive whiteboard controls to present learning content in exciting and dynamic ways. An interactive whiteboard allows you to model abstract ideas and concepts without touching the computer, change the model, move an object to another location on the screen, or establish new connections between objects. All this is done in real time.

2. Increasing student activity in the lesson

Many teachers claim that students become more active and interested in lessons that use an interactive whiteboard. Information becomes more accessible and understandable to them, which improves the atmosphere of understanding in the classroom, and students become more focused on their work.

3. Increasing the pace of the lesson. If you have an interactive whiteboard, during the lesson you will no longer have to wait for the student to write a task on the board, and several minutes of the lesson will be lost - the teacher can display pre-prepared materials on the screen, and the lesson time will be used only for solving the assigned tasks.

All entries on the interactive whiteboard can be saved on the computer and reopened when repeating the material covered or transferred to a student who missed a lesson due to illness.

Fully functioning interactive whiteboards typically include 4 components:

- computer
- multimedia projector
- appropriate software
- interactive board [2].

A multimedia projector and interactive whiteboard are connected to a computer. The image on the computer monitor is transmitted through the projector to the interactive whiteboard. Touches on the surface of the interactive whiteboard are transmitted to the computer using a cable or via infrared communication and are interpreted by special software installed on the computer.

Interactive whiteboards can be forward or rear projection. For forward projection, the projector is in front of the interactive whiteboard surface; for rear projection, it is behind the surface. Some models of interactive whiteboards can be equipped with special handheld computers for exchanging data with the interactive whiteboard.

More expensive models of interactive whiteboards do not use a projector, but are a large touch-screen plasma panel.

There are 3 types of interactive whiteboards:

Boards that fix the resistance of the surface when touched. These boards have a soft, flexible surface similar to two-piece vinyl. The material that fixes the resistance is separated by a small gap from the rest of the surface of the board and transmits signals to the computer when a special membrane is triggered. Such boards can be controlled not only with special markers, but also by touching the board with your hands or other objects. Special markers can be configured (in the included software) to display different colors.

Boards that record electromagnetic pulses. These boards are similar to traditional ones - their surface is hard. They are controlled by special electromagnetic pens (markers) powered by batteries. The surface of the board is covered with a grid of thin wires that capture the small magnetic field emitted by the marker.

Laser boards. These boards have a solid work surface with infrared laser scanners mounted on the surface. These scanners detect the movement of a special pen, the encoded color and transmit it to the computer.

We examined the possibilities offered by the use of an interactive whiteboard in education, and we were convinced that an interactive whiteboard is a modern tool that makes school learning more effective.

Most of the listed shortcomings are not so serious as to lead to the idea of refusing to use interactive software in the educational process.

Working with an interactive whiteboard in elementary school becomes a continuation of the game, accompanied by sound and video effects. After all, the use of various magnetic pens, laser pointers, and "magic" wands develops not only logic, creative thinking, motor skills and coordination of the child, but also allows him to go back, see where mistakes were made, and analyze his work.

It is important to note that increasing the effectiveness of learning in elementary school does not happen on its own with the purchase of an interactive whiteboard. It is important for the teacher to select material for lessons or to do it independently at the proper level.

References

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